

Open Research for Net Zero

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“The power of open research has never been more clearly demonstrated than in recent years with the effective collaboration and knowledge-sharing in the global race to find a vaccine for coronavirus.”

The changes required for environmentally sustainable computing are often synergic and overlapping with effective data management practices, efficient resource usage, and Open Research. Our aspiration is that a net zero Digital Research Infrastructure reached under these conditions will leverage wider benefits to the research community and wider society, beyond the net zero target.

Research in all disciplines increasingly relies on the use of Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI). As well as being integral to a healthy research culture and environment, open research and FAIR¹ (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable & Reusable) data practices can also promote more efficient and collaborative use of the DRI.

What is Open research?

Open research, also referred to as open science, relates to how research is performed and knowledge is shared based on the principle that research should be as open as possible.

Transparency, openness, verification and reproducibility are important features of research and innovation. Open research helps to support and uphold these features across the whole lifecycle of research – improving public value, research integrity, reuse and innovation.²

Open research also helps to support collaboration within and across disciplines.

The implementation of open research and FAIR data practices largely involves use of digital and collaborative technology, making the impacts of open research important for the UKRI DRI roadmap to Net Zero.

What is FAIR data?

The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship provide guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. FAIR data should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary (e.g. when it is not appropriate to openly publish data). These guidelines can be extended from data to supporting code, software and other tools that use DRI to conduct research.

Findable - Metadata and data should be easy to find for both humans and computers.

Accessible - Information required about how data can be accessed. Even if data is restricted, metadata should still be available.

¹ [FAIR Principles - GO FAIR \(go-fair.org\)](https://www.go-fair.org/)

² [Open research – UKRI](#)

Interoperable - Data should be available in a non-proprietary format where possible so it can be opened by anyone, or information should be provided alongside about how to use/where to get necessary software.

Reusable - Information to promote reuse of data: metadata, licence describing any conditions and how data can be used, how, why and who created and processed the data.

Embedding FAIR principles within research practices is a key aspect of open research. Ensuring that data is not only available to others but fully accessible and re-usable both adds value and credibility to data products and also reduces unnecessary data and code duplication. In turn, this enhances efficient use of DRI resources.

The benefits of open research for Net Zero DRI

- Developing Open Science and FAIR data standards, and providing training for researchers in these will maximise good practice, efficiency, data sharing, discoverability and reuse.
- Allowing others to review and reuse data and software used for research promotes efficient and effective use of the DRI by reducing unnecessary data duplication and replication.
- Reducing duplication of data increases efficiency of DRI use through both removing the compute effort of re-creating the data and also reducing the need for extra storage which makes better use of embodied carbon in data storage systems.
- Collaborating in code writing for research can further reduce duplication of effort and increase efficiency of DRI use through sharing of best practices in code design - learning from each other.
- Making research open and accessible extends the reach and impact of research outside academia.

The challenges

Making research open whilst maintaining credit where credit is due is far from easy. There is a strong correlation between papers with open data having more citations than similar papers that don't.³ However, for open research practices to be accepted, rightful credit must be given to authors whose research and data is made open. Robust open data policies and standards can ensure that credit is correctly given to authors of open data. Embargos give authors fair first-use. Clear, correctly chosen licences provided alongside the data/code support researchers whilst allowing data to be opened for wider use.

FAIRification⁴ of data can incur significant cost. The process of making data FAIR requires an ecosystem of supporting tools and services that in turn require DRI resources, such as long-term data preservation, machine processing of data, training and upskilling. The balance between benefits and costs is currently poorly understood: a variety of influencing factors interact together to drive the generation and use of FAIR data. The balance in terms

³ [Open-access papers draw more citations from a broader readership | Science | AAAS](#)

⁴ [How to GO FAIR - GO FAIR \(go-fair.org\)](#)

of net zero between effort put in and benefits derived is still unclear particularly when considering long term factors.⁵

To combat this as best we can, we need to think critically about the data we store and its value to others for long-term preservation. This means making valuable datasets and software open and FAIR whilst not using resources to store data unnecessarily by clumping all output together.

A vision for UKRI DRI in 2040

“The UKRI DRI reputation for environmental excellence and its leading role in promoting productivity through Open Science policies and workflows attracts leading researchers from all over the world.”

Adopting open research practices for net zero strengthens the case for existing UKRI policies and strategies like the NERC data policy, and open science strategies. A very large reduction in DRI energy requirements could be achieved simply by computing less and sharing existing results more effectively.

Further information

[FAIR Principles - GO FAIR \(go-fair.org\)](https://go-fair.org/)

[Open research – UKRI](#)

[Open research explained | Open research | Library | University of Leeds](#)

UNESCO (2021): Recommendation on Open Science

<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>

[NERC data policy](#)

Supporting recommendations

A general discussion of the recommendations can be found in section 3.2 of the [Net Zero DRI Scoping Project's final technical report: Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure](#)⁶.

A full list of the recommendations can be found in Appendix 3 of the final report and in addition can be accessed via this [spreadsheet](#).

Recommendation 148: Develop open science and FAIR data standards. Develop Open Science and FAIR data standards and train researchers in them to maximise good practice, efficiency, data sharing, discoverability and reuse.

Recommendation 15: Develop standards for Open Science principles. Open Science becomes common in the UKRI research community, leading to greater research efficiency

Recommendation 18: Adopt standards for research practice using DRI. Open Science enables greater efficiency in scientific workflows

⁵ Friday, A. (2023) 'Learning from the Big Picture: Applying Responsible Innovation to the Net Zero Research Infrastructure Transformation (ARINZRIT)'. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7966424>

⁶ Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>

Recommendation 24: Establish and promote sector-wide FAIR data and code protocols to maximise visibility and re-use of existing data and code, and minimise duplicate or unnecessary processing and storage

Recommendation 31: Ensure researchers follow best practice in the sustainable use of DRI whilst recognising the need to advance knowledge, e.g., by reusing DRI, data and code where possible, ensuring new code is optimised, embedding FAIR data practices, and considering whether the proposed research or new DRI is really required.

Recommendation 129: Provide more information and encouragement to facilitate the workforce to collaborate when writing code: Make the workforce more aware of the energy implications in writing code and to encourage to collaborate.

Recommendation 50: Data capture, storage and access. Reduce the need or drive to reproduce data that already exists by encouraging communities to adopt more openness and data-sharing practices.

Recommendation 144: Enabling creative partnerships. Fund projects that enable cross-UKRI researchers to work together creatively to share perspectives and discuss solutions about how to implement changes for net zero DRI

Roadmap 15: Adopt standards for Open Science principles and apply across the DRI.